

Spurious Preferential Sampling in Lagrangian Velocity-Gradient Statistics from Euler-Advection Tracers

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Abstract

A common workflow for Lagrangian statistics from turbulence databases — query the velocity at tracer positions, advance positions with a single forward-Euler step, repeat — silently violates incompressibility of the numerical flow map. The tracers acquire an effective inertia, drift out of vortical regions, and accumulate in strain-dominated regions, biasing every enstrophy- or strain-weighted Lagrangian statistic. We quantify the effect using the Johns Hopkins Turbulence Database (JHTDB) and controlled 64^3 direct numerical simulations. For an enstrophy-weighted vorticity–strain alignment efficiency $\langle r \rangle_\omega$, the bias follows $\Delta \approx 0.21 (\Delta t_{\text{adv}}/\tau_\eta)^{0.78}$ over $\Delta t_{\text{adv}}/\tau_\eta \in [0.03, 0.85]$ at $Re_\lambda = 37$, saturating after ~ 50 – 100 advection steps. At a typical JHTDB query interval ($\Delta t = 0.0065$, $\Delta t/\tau_\eta \approx 0.15$ for `isotropic1024coarse`) the measured bias at $Re_\lambda = 433$ reaches $+0.07$ — a 25% relative error that is larger at higher Reynolds number than the low- Re scaling predicts. Because the exponent is sublinear, reducing the step size is an inefficient remedy; replacing forward Euler by a second-order midpoint step (one additional velocity query per step) removes the effect to within statistical accuracy. We describe a $t = 0$ self-test by which any existing tracer data set can be checked for this bias retroactively.

1 The problem

Public turbulence databases such as the JHTDB [1, 2] make canonical DNS data available through point queries: velocity, gradients, and other fields can be requested at arbitrary positions and times. The JHTDB also offers a server-side particle-tracking service (`getPosition`) with proper high-order integration [6]; however, a large class of user-side workflows — in particular those built on `getData`-type interfaces, where gradients are collected *along* the trajectory — advect tracers themselves, and a common pattern is

$$\mathbf{x}_{n+1} = \mathbf{x}_n + \Delta t \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_n, t_n), \quad (1)$$

i.e. forward-Euler advection with the query interval Δt as time step — typically a small multiple of the storage interval (here $\Delta t = 0.0065$, about three storage steps of `isotropic1024coarse`). The velocity field is incompressible, but the discrete flow map of (1) is not: its Jacobian is

$$\det(I + \Delta t \nabla u) = 1 + Q \Delta t^2 + O(\Delta t^3), \quad Q = -\frac{1}{2} \text{tr}[(\nabla u)^2], \quad (2)$$

and Q is positive precisely in vortical regions: the numerical flow map *expands* inside vortex cores and *expels* tracers from them. The tracers thus behave like weakly inertial particles and exhibit the well-known preferential concentration of heavy particles [3, 4, 5]: they leave vortex cores and oversample strain-dominated regions. Unlike genuine particle inertia, this clustering

is a pure numerical artefact, and it converges to a statistically stationary sampling bias after a transient of order 50–100 steps.

Any statistic that weights samples by local enstrophy, strain, or conditions on gradient magnitudes along trajectories inherits this bias. We demonstrate the effect on the enstrophy-weighted alignment efficiency

$$\langle r \rangle_\omega = \frac{\langle |\omega|^2 \hat{\omega} \cdot S \hat{\omega} / \lambda_1(S) \rangle}{\langle |\omega|^2 \rangle}, \quad (3)$$

where S is the strain-rate tensor, λ_1 its largest eigenvalue and $\hat{\omega}$ the vorticity direction; r measures which fraction of the maximal available stretching the vorticity actually samples. The quantity is convenient because it is dimensionless, bounded, and sensitive to the strain–vorticity geometry — precisely the features that preferential sampling distorts.

2 Evidence

2.1 A $t = 0$ identity and its violation

Three tracer ensembles were advected through `isotropic1024coarse` ($Re_\lambda = 433$) in a *paired design*: 2000 and 4000 tracers with Euler advection (1), and 2000 tracers with a midpoint scheme (Sec. 3; labelled ‘RK2’ in the figures), all seeded uniformly at random with *identical* initial positions (the 2000-tracer sets coincide point by point at $t = 0$) and all with $\Delta t = 0.0065 \approx 0.15 \tau_\eta$, where $\tau_\eta = (\nu/\varepsilon)^{1/2} \approx 0.0446$ is the Kolmogorov time of the dataset ($\nu = 1.85 \times 10^{-4}$, $\varepsilon \approx 0.093$), using the `givernylocal` interface with 4th-order Lagrangian interpolation and 4th-order finite-difference gradients.¹

At $t = 0$ the seeding is uniform, so all ensembles sample the Eulerian measure fairly and coincide at $\langle r \rangle_\omega(0) = 0.292$ — by construction for the paired sets, statistically for the 4000-tracer set. Their subsequent evolution separates cleanly (Fig. 1): both Euler ensembles drift to $\langle r \rangle_\omega \approx 0.36$ within 50–100 steps and stay there; the midpoint ensemble fluctuates around 0.28 with no trend. Because the paired sets share the database realization, the interpolation settings (including `temporal_method='none'`, identical for all ensembles), the initial positions, and the analysis pipeline, their divergence is attributable solely to the advection scheme.

This also provides a **retroactive self-test** for existing data sets: compute the statistic of interest as a function of time since seeding. A systematic drift away from the $t = 0$ value on a scale of tens of Kolmogorov times — in stationary forced turbulence, where no such drift belongs — is the fingerprint of sampling bias.

¹A 2018 JHTDB announcement reports an ingest issue for `isotropic1024coarse` at $t > 2.048$ affecting two grid planes ($i = N_x, j = N_y$). It touches all our tracer sets identically and cannot generate the differential drift reported here.

Figure 1: Enstrophy-weighted alignment efficiency (3) along tracer ensembles in JHTDB isotropic1024coarse ($Re_\lambda = 433$, $\Delta t = 0.15 \tau_\eta$, curves smoothed over 9 samples). All ensembles start at the unbiased Eulerian value 0.292 (dotted); the Euler-advected ensembles drift to ≈ 0.36 as spurious clustering builds up, the RK2-advected ensemble does not.

2.2 Paired control in a resolved DNS

To exclude database-specific causes, a forced stationary 64^3 pseudo-spectral DNS ($Re_\lambda = 37.5$, $k_{\max}\eta = 0.99$, spectral gradients with $\nabla \cdot u$ at machine precision) was run with two tracer sets of 1500 particles each, started at *identical* positions in the *same* realization: one advected by Euler, one by the midpoint rule, both with $\Delta t = 0.03 \tau_\eta$. Over $101 \tau_\eta$ the Euler set settles at $\langle r \rangle_\omega = 0.309$ [0.303, 0.313], the midpoint set at 0.298 [0.293, 0.303] (bootstrap 95% intervals over particles; paired difference +0.011). Fig. 2 shows the time series.

Figure 2: Paired control: identical flow realization, identical initial particle positions, only the advection scheme differs ($Re_\lambda = 37.5$, $\Delta t = 0.03 \tau_\eta$, smoothed).

2.3 Scaling with the advection step

In the same DNS configuration, seven tracer populations were carried simultaneously through one flow realization: a midpoint reference (updated every field step) and six Euler populations updated only every n field steps with a single jump $n \Delta t_{\text{field}} \mathbf{u}$, $n \in \{1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32\}$, mimicking database workflows with coarse query intervals. This spans $\Delta t_{\text{adv}}/\tau_\eta \in [0.027, 0.85]$. After discarding the clustering transient, the bias relative to the midpoint reference follows a clean power law (Fig. 3, left); a control run with the discarded transient tripled changes the coarse-step biases by less than 5%, confirming saturation. The fit gives

$$\Delta \langle r \rangle_\omega \approx 0.21 (\Delta t_{\text{adv}}/\tau_\eta)^{0.78}, \quad Re_\lambda = 37. \quad (4)$$

The mechanism is confirmed directly: the mean enstrophy at Euler-tracer positions, normalized by the midpoint reference, falls monotonically from 0.93 to 0.52 across the scan (Fig. 3, right) — the tracers increasingly avoid vortical regions.

Figure 3: Left: bias of $\langle r \rangle_\omega$ versus advection step, with power-law fit (4); the dotted line marks the query interval used in Sec. 2.1 ($\Delta t \approx 0.15 \tau_\eta$). Right: mean enstrophy sampled by the Euler tracers relative to the RK2 reference — direct evidence of progressive vortex avoidance.

Two aspects deserve emphasis. First, the exponent is *sublinear*: halving the step reduces the bias only by a factor 0.58, and even at $\Delta t = 0.03 \tau_\eta$ a 4% relative error remains — indeed, Eq. (4) still predicts a bias of +0.02 ($\approx 6\%$ relative) at the storage interval of `isotropic1024coarse` itself ($\Delta t = 0.002 \approx 0.045 \tau_\eta$). Refining the step is therefore an inefficient remedy. Second, the low- Re fit (4) predicts +0.05 at the JHTDB operating point $\Delta t/\tau_\eta = 0.15$, whereas the measured bias at $Re_\lambda = 433$ is +0.07: the prefactor grows with Reynolds number, plausibly through small-scale intermittency. The scaling law should thus be read as a lower-bound estimate when extrapolating to high Re .

3 Remedy

A single predictor step removes the effect to within our statistical accuracy:

$$\mathbf{x}^* = \mathbf{x}_n + \frac{\Delta t}{2} \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_n, t_n), \quad \mathbf{x}_{n+1} = \mathbf{x}_n + \Delta t \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}^*, t_n). \quad (5)$$

This frozen-time midpoint rule costs one additional velocity query per step (a 50% increase for gradient workflows that already issue two queries) and requires no temporal interpolation. With (5) the $Re_\lambda = 433$ ensemble shows no drift over 116 τ_η and reproduces the $t = 0$ Eulerian

value. Standard particle-tracking wisdom in the DNS community has long favoured higher-order schemes [7]; the point here is the *magnitude* of the damage done by the seemingly innocuous Euler shortcut in database workflows, and how cheaply it is avoided.

4 Which published statistics are at risk

Statistics evaluated at (or shortly after) seeding are unaffected: there the Eulerian measure is still sampled fairly. Once the clustering transient has passed, however, *any* average over tracer positions is distorted — the mean enstrophy sampled by the tracers itself drops to 0.52 of the true value at large steps (Fig. 3, right). Particularly at risk in published work are: statistics weighted by enstrophy, dissipation, or strain; conditional averages along trajectories (e.g. gradient statistics conditioned on local flow topology); Lagrangian correlation functions of gradient quantities at time lags beyond the clustering transient; and any ‘stationary’ value obtained by discarding an initial window — the discarded window is exactly where the sampling was still fair. For the alignment statistic (3) the error at standard settings is 25%; for statistics more strongly concentrated on vortical structures (enstrophy moments, cf. the 0.52 enstrophy ratio at large steps) it can be larger.

Reproducibility

All runs use the public testing token of the JHTDB (`isotropic1024coarse`) via `givernylocal`, and a self-contained 64^3 pseudo-spectral solver (NumPy only). All analysis and DNS scripts, together with the raw trajectory data sets of every ensemble used here (HDF5, JHTDB layout), are archived alongside this preprint in the same Zenodo record.

References

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